

On the Synthesis of some Substituted Chalcones

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Ten new chalcones have been prepared for pharmacological interest, by condensing piperonal, 6-bromopiperonal, furan-2-carboxaldehyde and thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde with appropriate ketones.

INTRODUCTION of a halogen atom into position 2 of a chalcone containing a methylenedioxy function, so as to result its conjugation with α, β -unsaturated carbonyl system, may be expected to enhance the antibacterial activity of the chalcone thus formed due to the combined effect of methylenedioxyphenyl function¹, halogen atom and extended conjugation². This has been achieved by a typical synthesis of 2,5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-4,5-methylenedioxychalcone (Ia) (Fig. 1) by the condensation of 6-bromopiperonal and 5-bromopeonol. The condensation was carried out in the presence of 50% KOH solution for 2 hr at 60° followed by acidification with acetic acid. The same procedure, with modification wherever necessary to avoid resin formation, was extended for the preparation of some related

and thiophen-2-carboxaldehyde with appropriate ketones. All these compounds are obtained in 60-80% yields, and particularly in the case of 5'-bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-3-(2-thienyl)acrylophenone (Ie), the preparation of which is recently reported in 50% yield by a different method⁴, is now obtained in improved yield and shorter time.

All the 2'-hydroxychalcones and 2'-hydroxychalcone analogues have been characterised by converting them to flavonols and chromones respectively by sodium peroxide method⁵, while the remaining ones are converted to their corresponding dibromides.

The infrared absorption spectra of these compounds (Ia-h, IIa-b) in KBr disc show two bands each in the region of 7.6 μ -7.8 μ and 10.2 μ -10.3 μ characteristic of *trans* ethylenic compounds. Further there is also seen the conjugated carbon carbon double bond band at 6.25 μ -6.4 μ . Carbonyl stretching frequency in the case of compounds (Ia-g) appears in the region of 6.1 μ -6.15 μ while in the case of compounds (Ih, IIa-b) it is found shifted to lower wavelength 5.975 μ -6.05 μ . These assignments are in agreement with those observed by Mahanty⁶ *et al.* in case of chalcones and 2'-hydroxychalcones. Further the compounds (Ia-e) do not show characteristic hydroxyl band in the region of 2.85 μ but when these are cyclised to their respective chromone derivatives (IIIa-e) there appears a medium sharp band between 2.93 μ -3.1 μ and a strong band between 6.2 μ -6.25 μ which are due to the hydroxyl group and the carbonyl group of flavonols respectively.⁷

I a-h

III a-e

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R
a	OH	OCH ₃	Br	2-Bromo-4,5-methylene-dioxyphenyl
b	OH	H	H	— do —
c	OH	OCH ₃	Br	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl
d	OH	OCH ₃	Br	2-Furyl
e	OH	OCH ₃	Br	2-Thienyl
f	H	OCH ₃	H	2-Bromo-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl
g	H	Br	H	— do —
h	H	Br	H	3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl

II a: R = H

b: R = Br

Fig. 1.

chalcones and chalcone analogues by condensing piperonal, 6-bromopiperonal, furan-2-carboxaldehyde

Experimental

Preparation of chalcones and chalcone analogues :

Type A : (Ia-e). Aqueous KOH solution (20 ml., 50% w/v) was added to an ethanolic solution (approx. 10% w/v) of the acetophenone (0.02 mole) and the aldehyde (0.03 mole). The reaction mixture was maintained at 60°. After 2 hr it was cooled, acidified with acetic acid and the precipitate collected was crystallised after usual washings.

Type B : (If-h). The condensation was carried out at room temperature for 8 hr employing KOH solution (20 ml., 20% w/v).

TABLE

Sl.No.	Compound	M.P. °C Nature	% Yield	Molecular formula
Ia.	2,5'-Dibromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-4,5-methylenedioxychalcone	252° Golden yellow ^a microcrystals	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Br ₂ O ₅
b.	2-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-4,5-methylene-dioxychalcone.	155° Pale yellow ^b microcrystals	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrO ₄
c.	5'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-3,4-methylenedioxychalcone.	210° Yellow shining ^b flat needles	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrO ₅
d.	5'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-3-(2-furyl)-acrylophenone.	163°-164° Yellow shining ^b flakes	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrO ₄
e*.	5'-Bromo-2'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone.	178° Orange shining ^b cubes	85	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrO ₃ S
f.	2-Bromo-4'-methoxy-4,5-methylene-dioxychalcone.	157° Colourless tiny ^b needles	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrO ₄
α, β-Dibromide	181°d Colourless ^c rectangularflakes	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Br ₂ O ₄
g.	2,4'-Dibromo-4,5-methylene-dioxychalcone.	212° Colourless silky ^b needles	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Br ₂ O ₃
α, β-Dibromide	170°d Colourless needles ^c	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Br ₂ O ₃
h.	4'-Bromo-3,4-methylenedioxychalcone	138° Colourless stout ^e shining needles	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrO ₃
α, β-Dibromide	165°d Colourless flakes ^c	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Br ₂ O ₃

TABLE

Sl.No.	Compound	M.P. °C Nature	% Yield	Molecular formula
IIa.	1-(2-Furyl)-3-(3,4-methylene dioxypheyl)-2-propene-1-one.	128° Pale yellow ^e shining needles	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄
2,3-dibromide	152°d Colourless cubes ^c	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ Br ₂ O ₄
b.	1-(2-Furyl)-3-(2-bromo-4,5-methylene-dioxypheyl)-2-propene-1-one.	165° Pale yellow ^b silky needles	80	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrO ₄
2,3-dibromide	182° Colourless flakes ^c	80	C ₁₄ H ₈ Br ₂ O ₄
IIIa.	2',6-Dibromo-7-methoxy-4',5'-methylenedioxyflavonol.	255° Colourless shining ^c needles	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ Br ₂ O ₆
b.	2'-Bromo-4',5'-methylene-dioxyflavonol.	234° Yellow shining ^e spearlike flakes	55	C ₁₆ H ₉ BrO ₅
d.	6-Bromo-7-methoxy-3',4'-methylene-dioxyflavonol.	262° Colourless shining hairlike needles.	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ BrO ₆
d.	6-Bromo-2-(2-furyl)-3-hydroxy-7-methoxychromone.	226° Brownish yellow ^e stout rods	60	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrO ₅
e.	6-Bromo-2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-7-methoxychromone.	238° Rectangular ^e yellow flakes	60	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrO ₄ S

a = Ethyl acetate, b = Ethyl acetate + Ethyl alcohol, c = Acetic acid, e = Ethyl alcohol. All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C and H elements.

* Literature m.p. 178°-79°.

Type C: (IIa-b). As in type B except that the reaction temperature was 10°.

Preparation of flavonols and chromones: (IIIa-e):

To a suspension of chalcone or acrylphenone (Ia-e) (1 g.) in boiling ethyl alcohol (50 ml.), sodium-peroxide (2 g.) was added portionwise over a period of one half hour and heating under reflux was continued totally for two hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled and acidified with concentrated H₂SO₄ and the precipitate collected was crystallised.

Preparation of dibromides:

Bromine in acetic acid (5 ml., 10% w/v) was added to a solution of chalcone or chalcone analogue (If-h, IIa-b) (0.003 mole) in acetic acid and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. The crystalline dibromide separated was collected, washed with petroleum ether and dried. Additional amount of dibromide was obtained on dilution of the mother liquor with water. All the dibromides on boiling with KI in acetone regenerated respective chalcones.

All these compounds (Ia-h), IIa and IIb were tested for their antibacterial activity following the procedure of Gould and Bowie⁸ employing two organisms *S. aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The standard drugs used being 4,4'-sulphonyldianiline and chloramphenicol. Preliminary results of the testing were not encouraging.

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